

significantly less susceptibility to isolates of one species may be highly susceptible to another.

Three characteristics can distinguish the four species. *P. fuscovaginae* and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* produce a fluorescent blue pigment on King's B medium; *P. avenae* and *P. glumae* do not. Within each pair, the ability to use arginine for growth distinguishes the species—*P. fuscovaginae* and *P. glumae* are positive and *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* and *P. avenae* are negative. *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola* also can utilize sucrose, the others cannot. These characteristics suggest components of a simple culture medium on which the four species could be differentiated.

We prepared 3 differentiating media from this basal medium: Ayers et al mineral salts medium (NH₄H₂PO₄, 1.0 g; KCl, 0.2 g; MgSO₄ 7H₂O, 0.2 g; bromothymol blue (1.6% alcohol solution), 1.0 ml; distilled water to 11 and 12 g bacteriological agar (OXOID No. 1); pH adjusted to 7.2.

For the first differentiating medium, 1.0 g arginine was added by millipore filtration to the autoclave sterilized basal medium. For the second medium, 1.0 g arginine was added to the basal medium and then the whole was autoclaved. For the third medium, bromothymol blue was omitted from the basal medium and 1.0 g arginine added by millipore filtration. Virulent isolates of 30 *P. avenae*, 88 *P. fuscovaginae*, 10 *P. syringae*, and 6 *P. glumae* were streaked onto the different media; growth and fluorescence under black light were evaluated at 24 h. Approximately 1 ml 1.5% sucrose solution was added to plates where isolates showed no growth after 48 h and growth and fluorescence checked again after 24 h.

Only the medium with bromothymol blue and arginine added by filtration distinguished the isolates. The results are presented in the table.

Growth plus fluorescence indicated *P. fuscovaginae*; growth with no fluorescence indicated *P. glumae*; no growth for 48 h but growth following addition of sucrose indicated *P. syringae* pv. *oryzicola*; no growth following addition of sucrose indicated *P. avenae*.

Differential reactions^a of 4 *Pseudomonas* spp. on medium with bromthymol and arginine (prepared by filtration).

Species	Arginine medium		Sucrose added ^b	
	Growth	Fluorescence	Growth	Fluorescence
<i>P. avenae</i>	–	...	–	...
<i>P. glumae</i>	+	–
<i>P. fuscovaginae</i>	+	+
<i>P. syringae</i> pv. <i>oryzicola</i>	–	...	+	+

^a– = negative reaction, + = positive reaction, ... = not applicable. ^b1 ml sucrose added only if no growth was observed after 48 h.

The isolates identified using this medium must be pure, and their origins from rice and their pathogenicity on rice certain. The agar used must be bacteriological grade. Since whether or

not the pathogen produces fluorescent pigment on King's B medium will be known prior to using the arginine medium, detecting fluorescence on this medium is not essential. □

Early rice blast (BI) outbreak in Nepal

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BI caused by *Pyricularia oryzae*, is an important disease in rainy season (Jul-Nov) rice in Nepal but has not been reported in the endemic form in the pre-rainy season (Mar-Jul). A BI disease survey was made in rice plots of the experimental farm and adjoining

farmers' fields in Jhapa district (eastern BI-prone area) 13 May 1988 and 7 Jul 1988. Percent diseased leaf area was estimated on 100 randomly selected tillers per seedbed or per transplanted field.

Disease severity varied at seedling, maximum tillering, and dough stages (see table). Seedlings in Pusa-2-21 seedbeds were completely killed, and transplanted plants were heavily damaged by leaf and neck BI. This variety had been grown in this area for

BI disease severity in early rice of Nepal, 1988.

Field ^a	Date	Variety	Growth stage ^b	BI severity (%)	
				Leaf ^c	Neck ^d
<i>Jhapa</i>					
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	1	100	–
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	3	24	–
KAF	13 May	Pusa 2-21	3	33	–
KAF	13 May	Kankai 1	1	45	–
KAF	13 May	Kankai 1	3	12	–
KAF	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	18	52
KAF	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	20	68
KAF	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	3	12
FF1	7 Jul	Pusa 2-21	8	16	48
FF2	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	2	13
FF3	7 Jul	Kankai 1	8	2	21
<i>Chitwan</i>					
FF1	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	7
FF2	9 Jun	CH45	8	2	8
FF3	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	3
FF4	9 Jun	CH45	8	2	13
FF5	9 Jun	CH45	8	<1	5

^aKAF = Kankai Agricultural Farm, FF = farmer's field. ^bGrowth stages based on Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9: 1 = seedling or transplanting, 3 = stem elongation, 8 = dough stage. ^cBased on rating scale of 0 (0%) to 10 (100%) on 100 randomly selected tillers/field. ^dBased on, number of rotten panicle neck on 100 tillers randomly selected.

10 yr without any appreciable damage. Early rice varieties Bindeshwari, Chaite-2, and Chaite-4 had little or no disease.

In a survey of farmers' fields in Chitwan district (western BI-prone area) 9 Jun 1988, a low level of leaf BI and moderate level of neck BI were observed in rice variety CH-45, a popular early variety.

More than 100 mm rainfall occurred in May 1988, compared to less than 35 mm in May 1987. The rainfall also occurred more frequently. Thus, BI races able to attack the early varieties are prevalent in nature and cause serious yield losses in years of early rainfall. □

Isolation of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* with a semiselective medium (KBS)

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P. fuscovaginae, the causal agent of bacterial sheath brown rot of rice and first described in Japan, is now reported in several tropical countries (Burundi, Latin America, Madagascar).

Table 1. Composition of KBS medium.

Basal medium:	
Casamino acids (Difco)	20 g
Glycerol	15 ml
K ₂ HPO ₄	1.5 g
MgSO ₄ · 7H ₂ O	1.5 g
Agar	15 g
Distilled water	1 l

pH 7.0-7.2 adjusted with NaOH before autoclaving for 15 min at 121°C.

Components added to the melted basal medium at 45°C:

Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (= Cetrime, Labosi)	5 ml of a distilled water stock solution (20 mg/ml)
Trimethoprim (Sigma)	20 mg
Penicillin G (Sigma)	50 mg
Bacitracin (Sigma)	20 mg
Cycloheximide (=Actidione, Labosi)	50 mg

The last 4 components were mixed in 4 ml of 70% ethanol.

Symptoms are similar to those produced by other pathogens: grain discoloration, sheath necrosis, and spikelet sterility.

Isolation of *P. fuscovaginae* is difficult, particularly on older or deteriorated samples, because of the presence of other bacteria commonly isolated from rice samples. We developed a semiselective medium (KBS) that can be used to isolate *P. fuscovaginae* on different rice samples.

Composition of the KBS medium is detailed in Table 1. Basal medium is King's medium B (KB), but the source of peptone has been changed. Proteose peptone n°3 is replaced by casamino acids. This is important because the pigment produced by some strains (particularly from Madagascar) fluoresced only weakly or not at all in ultraviolet light when bacterial growth occurred on KB medium containing proteose peptone n°3, bacto-peptone, or casitone (Difco).

Plating efficiencies of 4 reference strains of *P. fuscovaginae* on KBS medium ranged from 5 to 100% after 3

Table 2. Plating efficiency on KBS medium of *Pseudomonas fuscovaginae* from distilled water suspensions.

Strain	Source	Plating efficiency ^a (%)
GR 2	Madagascar	100 ^b
HMB 264	Burundi	100 ^b
6801	Japan	5
		60 ^c
BCE 32	Colombia	100 ^b

^a Plating efficiency = colony-forming units recovered on KBS + colony-forming units on KB × 100. ^b After 3 d incubation at 28°C. ^c After 6 d incubation at 28°C.

d of incubation, and from 60 to 100% after 6 d of incubation at 28 °C (Table 2). Other fluorescent pseudomonads and a few other bacterial species grew on KBS medium, but development of most saprophytic bacteria and fungi was inhibited.

We used different media to isolate *P. fuscovaginae* on several hundred rice samples. KBS medium was the most useful, especially when laboratory facilities are limited. □

Insect management

Morphometric comparison of stridulating organs of brown planthopper (BPH) infesting rice and *Leersia* grass

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BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) males and females communicate prior to copulation, by means of acoustic courtship signals emitted by specialized stridulating organs located at the junction of the metathorax and abdomen on each side of the body. Each organ comprises a sclerotized meta-coxata and a petal-like abdominal sclerite extended in front of the third sternopleuron.

As a calling adult slightly vibrates its abdomen in a dorsoventral direction, the sclerite rubs against the top of the

coxata, emitting discrete sound pulses, or clicks. The wave patterns, pulse repetition frequencies, and sonic spectra of acoustic signals have been found to differ significantly in BPH infesting rice and BPH infesting the weed grass *Leersia hexandra* Swartz.

To find out why acoustic signals differ in the two populations, we compared the stridulating organs (length, width, number of chitinous scales on coxata and sclerite) of males and females from each population.

We used an aspirator to collect 20 brachypterous males and 20 females from a BPH population maintained on TN1 rice plants and from a population reared on *Leersia* plants. The insects were prepared for morphological examination as follows: 1) boil in 95% ethyl alcohol in a water bath for 5 min; 2) macerate in 10% lukewarm NaOH for 15 min; 3) wash with 95% ethyl alcohol and boil in chloral-phenol (1:1 part chloral hydrate and phenol crystals) for 20 min; 4) orient and mount left and